

A Review on: Mosquito Repellent Activity of Herbal Plants

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Abstract:

Mosquito-borne diseases are a major public health issue worldwide. Chemical repellents, although effective, pose environmental and health risks, prompting interest in plant-based alternatives. As a result, natural plant-based repellents have garnered increased attention due to their eco-friendly, non-toxic, and cost-effective properties. This review evaluates the mosquito-repellent properties of six plants: Neem, Tulsi, Lemongrass, Bay Leaf, Eucalyptus, and Clove, exploring their bioactive compounds, extraction techniques, and evaluation methods.

Introduction:

Mosquitoes transmit diseases like malaria, dengue, and Zika, making mosquito control essential. Synthetic repellents like DEET are widely used but have safety concerns. Natural repellents from plants are gaining attention as they offer a safer, eco-friendly alternative. Neem, Tulsi, Lemongrass, Bay Leaf, Eucalyptus, and Clove are widely used

in traditional medicine for their insect-repellent properties. This review highlights their effectiveness, extraction, and evaluation methods.

Active Compounds and Mosquito-Repellent Properties

1. Neem (*Azadirachta indica*):

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Sapindales

Family: Meliaceae

Genus: *Azadirachta*

Species: *A. indica*

Neem has a long history of medicinal use in Ayurvedic medicine. The primary mosquito-repellent compound in neem is azadirachtin, an insect growth regulator that disrupts the life cycle of mosquitoes.

Repellent Properties: Neem oil, both in its pure form and mixed with coconut oil, provides significant protection against mosquito bites. Studies have demonstrated that neem-based repellents are effective against *Anopheles*, *Aedes*, and *Culex* species.

Mode of Action: Neem oil works by interfering with hormone production in mosquitoes, disrupting molting, mating, and reproduction. Azadirachtin also has an antifeedant effect, deterring mosquitoes from landing on treated skin.

Active Compounds: Azadirachtin, nimbin, and salannin.

2. Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*):

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Lamiales

Family: Lamiaceae

Genus: *Ocimum*

Species: *O. tenuiflorum*

Tulsi, also known as holy basil, is a popular medicinal herb known for its antimicrobial and insecticidal properties.

Repellent Properties: Tulsi oil contains eugenol, methyl eugenol, and carvacrol, all of which exhibit strong insect-repellent properties. The essential oil of Tulsi has demonstrated repellency against *Aedes* and *Culex* mosquitoes. Research has shown that the essential oil of Tulsi provides protection against *Aedes* and *Culex* mosquitoes.

Mode of Action: The volatile compounds in Tulsi oil have a fumigant effect that repels mosquitoes by affecting their olfactory receptors. Additionally, eugenol has an anesthetic effect, discouraging mosquitoes from landing on exposed skin.

Active Compounds: Eugenol, methyl eugenol, and carvacrol.

3. Lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*):

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Poales

Family: Poaceae

Genus: Cymbopogon

Species: C. nardus

Lemongrass, recognized for its strong citrus scent, is rich in citral, which is responsible for its insect-repellent action.

Repellent Properties: Lemongrass oil has shown up to 95% effectiveness against mosquito bites when applied as a topical repellent. It is effective against multiple mosquito species, including Anopheles and Aedes.

Mode of Action: Citral interferes with mosquito olfactory receptors, masking the carbon dioxide and other human skin odors that attract mosquitoes. This compound also affects the central nervous system of mosquitoes, reducing their biting tendency.

Active Compounds: Citral and geraniol.

4. Bay Leaf (*Laurus nobilis*):

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Laurales

Family: Lauraceae

Genus: Laurus

Species: L. nobilis

The main components of bay leaf are Bay leaves, derived from the bay laurel tree (*Laurus nobilis*), contain various bioactive compounds, including Volatile Components: 1,8-Cineole (30-50%), Linalool (10-20%), Pinene (5-15%), Beta-pinene (5-10%), Limonene (2-5%).

Bay leaf, widely used in culinary applications, contains eucalyptol, linalool, and α -terpineol, which are effective insect repellents.

Repellent Properties: Studies have shown that bay leaf oil provides moderate repellent activity against *Aedes* mosquitoes. Bay leaf extracts have been used in the formulation of natural insect repellents and have demonstrated lasting effects.

Mode of Action: Bay leaf essential oil affects mosquito behavior by disrupting their olfactory sense. Eucalyptol and linalool mask human scent, making it challenging for mosquitoes to locate their host.

Active Compounds: Eucalyptol, linalool, and α -terpineol.

5. Eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus globulus*):

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Myrtales

Family: Myrtaceae

Genus: Eucalyptus

Species: *E. globulus*

Eucalyptus oil, particularly lemon eucalyptus (*Corymbia citriodora*), is a highly effective mosquito repellent, containing p-menthane-3,8-diol (PMD), which is registered with the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) as a mosquito repellent.

Repellent Properties: Eucalyptus oil has shown comparable effectiveness to DEET in some studies. It is effective against Anopheles and Aedes mosquitoes and can provide protection for up to 6 hours post-application.

Mode of Action: PMD acts on mosquitoes' olfactory receptors, masking human odor cues and creating a scent barrier. It also acts as an irritant, repelling mosquitoes from treated surfaces.

Active Compounds: p-menthane-3,8-diol (PMD).

6. Clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*):

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Myrtales

Family: Myrtaceae

Genus: *Syzygium*

Species: *S. aromaticum*

Clove is a well-known spice with high concentrations of eugenol, which possesses potent insecticidal and repellent properties.

Repellent Properties: Clove oil is an effective mosquito repellent, particularly when combined with other essential oils like coconut or soybean oil. Research has demonstrated that clove oil can provide 2-3 hours of protection against Aedes mosquitoes.

Mode of Action: Eugenol affects mosquito olfactory and gustatory receptors, reducing their attraction to human skin. Additionally, it acts as an anesthetic, discouraging mosquitoes from remaining on treated skin.

Active Compounds: Eugenol.

Extraction Techniques

Extraction techniques play a critical role in isolating the bioactive compounds from these plants:

1. Steam Distillation: Commonly used for essential oils (e.g., from lemongrass, eucalyptus, clove). The plant material is boiled, and the steam is condensed to separate the oil.

2. Hydrodistillation: Similar to steam distillation, used for oils with low boiling points like neem and tulsi.

3. Cold Press Extraction: Suitable for delicate compounds that degrade under heat (mainly applied in neem oil extraction).

4. Solvent Extraction: Uses organic solvents like ethanol or hexane to extract active compounds, followed by evaporation of the solvent.

5. Supercritical Fluid Extraction (SFE): Utilizes supercritical CO₂ to extract compounds without residual solvents, maintaining compound integrity.

Evaluation Methods for Mosquito-Repellent Activity

The efficacy of plant-based repellents can be assessed using the following evaluation methods:

1. **Arm-in-Cage Test:** A volunteer's arm is treated with the repellent and placed in a cage containing mosquitoes. The number of bites within a set time frame measures repellency.
2. **Field Trials:** Repellents are applied to human volunteers in natural habitats with high mosquito density. The protection time and biting reduction are recorded.
3. **Y-Tube Olfactometer:** Tests mosquito attraction to treated versus untreated arms using air-flow tubes, allowing comparison of mosquito preference.
4. **Landing-Biting Count Method:** Mosquitoes are observed for landing and biting behavior on a treated surface. The percentage reduction in bites measures repellency.
5. **Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) Analysis:** Identifies active compounds and assesses stability, volatility, and persistence of repellent oils over time.

Comparative Effectiveness and Safety

Plant-based repellents are generally safer for humans and the environment compared to synthetic alternatives. However, some plant oils can cause mild skin irritation and require dilution with carrier oils. Efficacy varies by plant type and formulation, with eucalyptus, clove, and lemongrass showing longer protection duration.

Conclusion

Neem, Tulsi, Lemongrass, Bay Leaf, Eucalyptus, and Clove demonstrate significant potential as natural mosquito repellents. Their bioactive compounds show strong repellent properties, and the diverse extraction and evaluation methods optimize their formulation. The integration of these natural repellents into public health measures could reduce the global burden of mosquito-borne diseases, providing an eco-friendly alternative to synthetic repellents.

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